

Secure and Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning in Healthcare using Partial Homomorphic Encryption

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Abstract—Secure and privacy-preserving machine learning in healthcare has the potential to enhance diagnostics and treatment while protecting patient confidentiality. This paper introduces a framework that integrates partial homomorphic encryption (PHE) with machine learning to enable robust data analysis in medical settings. Leveraging PHE allows for the encryption of sensitive medical data to maintain privacy while still enabling computational operations needed for machine learning algorithms. The framework's goal is to assist healthcare institutions in maximizing the use of machine learning techniques while respecting patient privacy rights. Case studies and demonstrations illustrate the effectiveness of the framework in facilitating secure data analysis in healthcare, emphasizing its importance in advancing medical research and enhancing patient care.

Keywords—Secure Machine Learning, Privacy-Preserving Data Analysis, Homomorphic Encryption, Healthcare, Patient Confidentiality.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of healthcare analytics, leveraging machine learning algorithms to derive insights from patient data is increasingly prevalent. However, a significant challenge arises concerning the privacy of sensitive medical information. Traditional data privacy approaches often involve encryption, yet these methods typically hinder the applicability of machine learning algorithms. Homomorphic Encryption (HE) emerges as a promising solution to this issue.

HE enables computations to be performed directly on encrypted data, preserving data privacy while allowing for meaningful analysis and inference. By leveraging HE, healthcare institutions can utilize machine learning to analyse medical datasets without compromising patient confidentiality. This paper explores the intersection of machine learning and partial homomorphic encryption (PHE) to address privacy concerns in healthcare data analytics. Through a review of existing literature and practical demonstrations, we elucidate the capabilities and implications of employing PHE in safeguarding patient privacy while advancing healthcare analytics.

Paillier Cryptosystem:

The Paillier cryptosystem operates with a distinctive probabilistic nature, generating unique encryption codes for

each ciphertext. This inherent randomness enhances security by making it difficult to determine whether two ciphertexts correspond to the same plaintext message. At its core, Paillier employs additive homomorphic encryption, enabling secure operations on encrypted data while maintaining confidentiality, integrity, and availability.

Homomorphic Encryption (Paillier Algorithm):

Initially conceptualized by Rivest, Dertouzos, and Adleman following the development of RSA, homomorphic encryption enables computations on encrypted data without decryption. The Paillier algorithm exemplifies additive homomorphism, facilitating binary addition operations on ciphertexts. Developed by Pascal Paillier in 1999, this algorithm efficiently encrypts multiple bits in a single operation with minimal expansion and streamlined decryption capabilities.

Key Generation:

Key generation in the Paillier cryptosystem involves selecting two large, mutually exclusive prime numbers (x and y) and computing their product (n). Additionally, a random integer (f) is chosen to ensure the security of the public key, while the private key includes the least common multiple of $(x-1)$ and $(y-1)$ (λ) and the multiplicative inverse of a certain function of $g^{\lambda} \bmod n^2$ (μ).

Encryption:

To encrypt a plaintext message (x), a random integer (r) is selected within specific parameters, and the ciphertext (c) is computed using a generator (g) according to the formula $c = g^x \cdot r^n \bmod n^2$.

Decryption:

Decryption involves extracting the original plaintext message (x) from the ciphertext (c) using the private key components (λ , μ) and a mathematical function. This process ensures that only authorized parties can access the original data while preserving its confidentiality.

Characteristics:

The Paillier algorithm exhibits several unique characteristics that contribute to its effectiveness in secure data processing. Notably, its homomorphic nature enables non-deterministic encryption and supports additive operations, allowing for computations on encrypted data without compromising security. Additionally, during addition operations, ciphertexts are multiplied to obtain the sum of the plaintext, enhancing the algorithm's robustness and versatility.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Jihyeon Ryu, Keunok Kim, Dongho Won [1] Homomorphic encryption techniques have garnered significant attention for their capability to securely process sensitive data in encrypted form. In a study conducted by Ryu, Kim, and Won, four partially homomorphic encryption methods, namely Paillier, ElGamal, ASHE, and Symmetria, are analyzed. Their research aims to compare and evaluate the key size and ciphertext size of these encryption schemes. By assessing the performance and cryptographic properties of each method, the authors provide valuable insights into the practical applicability of partially homomorphic encryption in securing data stored in cloud services.

Rajesh C R, Penakalapati Sesha Harshini, Tejashwini N, Chandini T R, D B Srinivas [2] In this research article, the authors propose a novel homomorphic encryption scheme based on multistage partial homomorphic encryption specifically designed for secure and efficient computations in cloud computing environments. The abstract emphasizes the importance of cloud computing as a prominent paradigm for data storage and processing, while highlighting the persistent concern over data security. The proposed scheme aims to address this concern by leveraging homomorphic encryption techniques to ensure secure and privacy-preserving data processing in the cloud.

Ailuan Zhang, Ziehen Li [3] propose a novel homomorphic encryption algorithm based on the Learning With Errors (LWE) problem, a significant area in post-quantum cryptography. The approach addresses limitations of existing schemes by introducing a new encryption algorithm based on LWE over integers, validated for correctness and security through theoretical analysis. Also, present an additive homomorphism algorithm derived from this encryption method, demonstrating its correctness and capability for multi-level homomorphic additions under specified parameters. Experimental simulations validate the correctness and efficiency of both algorithms compared to existing ones, showing notable efficiency advantages.

Zhanerke Temirbekova, Anna Pyrkova, Zukhra Abdiakhmetova, and Aidana Berdaly [4] explore fully homomorphic encryption (FHE) for secure data processing while preserving privacy. They propose and implement a comprehensive FHE library supporting all arithmetic operations, including division and subtraction. Their novel method enhances FHE's practicality, validated through numerical experiments for security and efficiency.

A Vijaya Kumar, Kollipara Cheedella Bhavana, and Yamini [5] address the growing popularity of cloud services and the associated need for robust data security measures. Despite the benefits of cloud storage, concerns about data breaches and access management persist. To mitigate these risks, encryption techniques are commonly employed. However, traditional encryption methods require data decryption for any operation, posing challenges for efficient data analysis and utilization. The authors propose a novel encryption technique tailored to address these challenges and ensure data security in cloud environments.

George Dimitoglou and Carol Jim [6] investigate the performance of three additively homomorphic encryption algorithms: Paillier, Damgård-Jurik, and ElGamal. Their study focuses on runtime analysis and comparison, evaluating variable key lengths during encryption and

homomorphic addition operations. By empirically assessing algorithmic complexity and computational speed, the research underscores the practical viability of homomorphic encryption for secure data computation in real-world applications.

Seongbong Choi; Hyung Tae Lee [7] In 2020, Omar and Abed introduced a noise-free fully homomorphic encryption scheme allowing computations on encrypted data without decryption. However, lacking a comprehensive security analysis, their scheme's vulnerability to known plaintext attacks is explored in this study. Simple algorithms leveraging GCD computations on minimal message-ciphertext pairs are demonstrated as effective attacks on their proposal.

Victor Kadykov, Alla Levina and Ksenia Grebenevich [8] In the era of exponential data transmission, the need to modify encrypted information without decryption poses significant challenges, particularly in cloud storage systems. Homomorphic Encryption (HE) emerges as a solution, enabling mathematical operations on encrypted data without decryption. This paper explores the benefits of HE in cloud computing, focusing on Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) and Partly Homomorphic Encryption (PHE). While FHE, introduced in 2009, has garnered attention, this study delves into the utilization of ideal lattices for constructing homomorphic operations on ciphertexts, offering insights for enhancing cloud security and efficiency.

III. MOTIVATION

Amidst the evolving healthcare landscape, the digitalization of medical records presents a dual challenge: the imperative to protect sensitive patient data while harnessing the potential of advanced analytics for improved patient care. With data breaches and privacy breaches on the rise, healthcare organizations grapple with the need for robust security measures without compromising the utility of patient data.

In response to these pressing concerns, this research embarks on a novel exploration: the fusion of Partial Homomorphic Encryption (PHE) with machine learning in healthcare. By melding cryptographic principles with predictive analytics, our approach endeavors to unlock the transformative power of data-driven insights while upholding patient privacy and confidentiality.

At its core, this endeavor is driven by a commitment to innovation and security in healthcare data management. By pioneering the integration of PHE into healthcare analytics workflows, we aspire to forge a path towards a future where data security and data utility coexist harmoniously. Through this pioneering research, we aim to lay the groundwork for a paradigm shift in healthcare analytics, where privacy-preserving machine learning becomes the cornerstone of data-driven healthcare innovation.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology involve the following steps:

1. Data preparation and Model Training
2. Homomorphic Encryption Setup

3. Server-Side Computation with PHE
4. Result Serialization and Transmission

Data Preparation and Model Training: This step involves selecting and preparing the dataset containing healthcare data. The data is cleaned, normalized, and features are engineered as needed. Then, a linear regression model is trained on this pre-processed dataset using standard machine learning techniques.

Homomorphic Encryption Setup: In this step, encryption keys required for Partial Homomorphic Encryption (PHE) are generated. These encryption keys are used to secure both the data and the computations performed on the data, ensuring privacy is maintained.

Server-Side Computation with PHE: The server performs computations directly on the encrypted data using Partial Homomorphic Encryption (PHE). This allows the server to process the data without fully decrypting it, thereby preserving the privacy of the sensitive healthcare information.

Result Serialization and Transmission: After performing computations on the encrypted data, the server serializes the computed results along with the encryption key used for encryption. These serialized results are then securely transmitted back to the customer for decryption.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

Customer side:

Required headers:

```
from linearmodel import LinModel
import phe as paillier
import json
```

Step 1: Encrypting the data using private and public key:

```
pub_key, priv_key = getKeys()
data = [45, 0, 1, 25.6, 130, 80, 105, 2]
serializeData(pub_key, data)
datafile=serializeData(pub_key, data)
with open('data.json', 'w') as file:
    json.dump(datafile, file)
```

Step 2: Load the answer received from the server:

```
answer_file=loadAnswer()
answer_key=paillier.PaillierPublicKey(n=int(
answer_file['pubkey']['n']))
answer =
paillier.EncryptedNumber(answer_key,
int(answer_file['values'][0]),
int(answer_file['values'][1]))
if (answer_key==pub_key):
    print(priv_key.decrypt(answer))
```

Model training:

```
df = pd.read_csv('CVD_report.csv')
y = df['CVD Risk Score']
X = df.drop('CVD Risk Score',
axis=1)
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test =
train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2,
random_state=0)
reg =
LinearRegression().fit(X_train, y_train)
```

Server Side:

Step1: computing the encrypted data from customer side:

```
def computeData():
    data = getData()
    mycoef = LinModel().getCoef()
    pk = data['public_key']
    pubkey =
paillier.PaillierPublicKey(n=int(pk['n']))
    encrypted_values = data['values']
    enc_nums_rec =
[paillier.EncryptedNumber(pubkey,
int(x[0]),int(x[1])) for x in
encrypted_values]
    results = sum([mycoef[i] *
enc_nums_rec[i] for i in
range(len(mycoef))])
    return results, pubkey
print(computeData()[0].ciphertext())
```

step 2: Serialize the computed result along with public key:

```
def serializeData():
    results, pubkey = computeData()
    encrypted_data={}
    encrypted_data['pubkey'] = {'n':
pubkey.n}
    encrypted_data['values'] =
(str(results.ciphertext()),
results.exponent)
    serialized =
json.dumps(encrypted_data)
    return serialized
print(serializeData())
```

VI. RESULT

```
print("Regression Coefficients:")
print(reg.coef_)
print("\nRoot Mean Squared Error
(RMSE):", RMSE)
print("R-squared (R^2):",
R_squared)
```

Regression Coefficients:
[0.88554603 7.25253036 15.5418905 -2.41864682 -0.48638537 0.65967963
0.19329526 10.22072479]

Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE): 8.675843863982607
R-squared (R²): 0.663668651875379

Server side:

Server Page

Encrypted Result:

3587669916446001911262337860520142743206897714445724
13112768782332592891018017796841401432763226114265661
36370428638605345693131493573652102030609123320976365
55598772979419541405955978654597217051200334425562247
13179957832271829260181799047780320806788543416040764
55047494749011145881914049702159980030397630958542593
68939775931077467831397112712282820881836447882434008
36297113709801770516073083615644981256899753635618567

Customer Side:

CVD Score Calculator

Age: 66 BMI: 56.3

Sex: Male Systolic BP: 130

Smoking Status: Current Smoker Diastolic BP: 120

FBS: 105

Physical Activity: Moderate

Submit

Server

CVD Score: 80.51344937926642

Server

VII. CONCLUSION

When the homomorphic encryption algorithm ensures security and the server cannot access the user's private key, it remains incapable of extracting plaintext data from ciphertext, thereby preserving the security of the data. This suggests the feasibility and applicability of homomorphic encryption in machine learning scenarios without compromising accuracy. Such an approach is particularly suitable for applications with stringent security demands.

VIII. FUTURE SCOPE

The future scope of the paper lies in exploring more advanced homomorphic encryption techniques and their integration with machine learning models in healthcare. Additionally, further research could focus on optimizing the efficiency and performance of homomorphic encryption algorithms to handle larger datasets and more complex computations. Moreover, investigating the practical implementation of homomorphic encryption in real-world healthcare systems and evaluating its scalability and usability would be valuable. Furthermore, exploring the potential applications of homomorphic encryption beyond healthcare, such as in finance, government, and other sensitive data domains, could uncover new opportunities and challenges for its adoption. Overall, the future of the paper entails continued exploration, experimentation, and refinement of homomorphic encryption techniques to enhance privacy-preserving machine learning in diverse domains.

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